

TUNED ATTRIBUTES AND MACHINE LEARNING MODELS FOR WATER QUALITY ASSESSMENT

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Abstract

Water quality classification is a critical task for environmental monitoring and public health. Existing research has explored various hyperparameter tuning techniques, including Grid Search, Random Search, Genetic Algorithm, and Chaos-Driven Bat Algorithm, to optimize machine learning (ML) models. However, there remains a need for a more efficient approach to both feature selection and hyperparameter tuning. This study proposes a hybrid optimization framework combining the Relief algorithm and Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO) to enhance water quality classification. First, the Relief algorithm and GWO are individually applied to select the most significant attributes from a Kaggle water quality dataset. The top two attributes identified by each method are then used for classification to improve model interpretability and performance. Next, GWO is employed for hyperparameter tuning to optimize ML model weights, ensuring improved accuracy and generalization. The framework is evaluated using four ML models: K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN), Decision Tree (DT), Random Forest (RF), and Support Vector Regression (SVR). Experimental results demonstrate that the proposed hybrid approach outperforms traditional tuning methods, achieving higher classification accuracy and robustness. This study highlights the effectiveness of integrating Relief and GWO for optimized feature selection and hyperparameter tuning, offering a scalable and efficient solution for water quality assessment.

Keywords: WQA, Tuned Attributes, tuned parameters, Grey Wolf optimizer, Relief algorithm, ML

1. Introduction

Water is an essential resource for all living organisms to ensure sustainable life and maintain balanced ecological conditions. In particular, clean water is required for drinking, as well as for

activities such as agriculture, industry, power generation, and biodiversity conservation. Water quality is highly impacted by urbanisation, increasing population, and industrial discharges. These factors affect both surface water quality and groundwater levels [1]. According to the report [2], more than two billion people are estimated to lack access to clean water, and they are also subjected to waterborne diseases such as cholera, typhoid, and dysentery.

Water safety and cleanliness are important factors for ecological maintenance. Poor water quality degrades the aquatic environment, which disrupts natural processes like nutrient cycling and flood regulation, and it leads to biodiversity threats [3]. Apart from these factors, climate change has a higher impact on water bodies. Global warming also contributes to increased floods and droughts, which makes water management a challenge for a sustainable environment. The aforementioned information states that the continuous monitoring of water bodies are required to ensure the good water quality.

A. Role of water Quality Indicators

Water quality can be assessed using various indicators such as physical, chemical, biological and microbiological parameters [4] & [5] as shown in the figure 1. These parameters to detect both natural and anthropogenic influences in the water.

Figure 1. WQI

Each indicator has unique factors for analysing the WQ. For example, in physical, the turbidity, total suspended solids, temperature and electrical conductivity of the water is analysed to understand the physical condition of water. Chemical indicators such as pH, dissolved oxygen, nitrates, phosphates and biochemical oxygen demand are all used to analyse the water degradation level. Biological indicators analyse the aquatic organisms like phytoplankton, fish and macroinvertebrates to measure the ecosystem health. Microbiological indicators assess the presence of bacteria like E. coli, which can cause hazards to human health. The main purpose of this indicator is presented in the figure 2.

Figure 2. WQI purpose

WQI values are often presented in the numeral format which was difficult to understand its interpretation. This problem was overcome by implementing the techniques proposed in [6] to convert this numerical information into an understandable score.

The present advanced technologies help to estimate the water quality as well as the relationship between the WQI indicators and the WQ.

2. Related Works

This section summarised the machine learning and statistical analysis-based water quality analysis using different input forms such as images and water quality indicators.

Table 1. Summarization of WQ analysis

Author	Water Source	Input type	Techniques	Evaluation metrics	Observation
Ma et al., (2021)	Lakes and rivers	Sentinel 2 images of North east China	Regression Models	Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Mean Square Error (MSE) and R ²	Optimized Hyperparameter based Random Forest algorithm can estimate water quality using B2 to B5 spectral bands.
Kouadari et al., (2021)	Ground water sources	Physical and chemical indicators from the Illizi region	Multi linear regression (MLR), M5P tree, RF, Random subspace, Artificial Neural Network (ANN), SVR, Locally Weighted Linear Regression (LWLR) and Additive	Relative Absolute Error (RAE), Root Relative Square Error (RRSE), MSE, RMSE and Correlation (R)	Total suspension solids are key indicators for an accurate estimation using MLR algorithms

			Regression		
Al Sulttani et al., (2021)	Euphrates river	Physical and chemical indicators.	Quantile Regression Forest, RF, Gradient boosting machines, Stochastic Gradient Boosting	RMSE, R^2 , MAE, Willmott index (d), PBIAS	PCA based QRF estimates biochemical oxygen demand effectively than other algorithms.
Kaur et al., (2021)	Charles river	Physical and chemical Indicators	RF and CART with PCA	Accuracy, Precision, Recall and F1 score	PCA enhances the water quality.
Rodriguez et al., (2021)	River (Uruguay)	Physical and chemical	Inverse Distance Weighting (IDW), RFR, SVR, Regressor types RF,KNN, Ridge, Huber and Adaboost	Kling Gupta Efficiency (KGE), PB, Nash Sutcliffe Efficiency.	IDW outperforms other techniques.
Aslam et al.,(2022)	River (Pakistan)	Physical and chemical	RT, RF, REPT and it	RMSE, MAE, NSE, PB	Hybrid RT ANN estimates the WQ effectively than other hybrid models.
Suwadi et al., (2022)	Langat basin (Malyasia)	Physical and chemical	ANN, SVM, RF, NB	Accuracy, Recall, Precision	RF can estimate WQ effectively using BOD, COD and DO
Juna et al., (2022)	Kaggle dataset	Physical and chemical	KNN with ML and 9-layer MLP	Accuracy, Precision, Recall,	KNN based data balance enhanced the MLP results.
Malek et al., (2022)	Kelantan river	Physical and chemical	ML models	Accuracy, Precision and Recall.	GB estimates the WQ effectively than other techniques. In particular, TSS is an effective WQ indicators.
Ajayi et al., (2022)	Cape Town city Lakes.	Physical and chemical	ML models	Accuracy	SVM model produces the best results with Recursive feature elimination.
Chakravarthy et al., (2023)	Kaggle Dataset	Physical and chemical	Adaptive crow search and Soft max Extreme learning machine	Accuracy, Precision, Recall	CSO predicts that the Softmax activation function is beset for the ELM to estimate the WQ effectively.
Ashgar et al, (2023)	Water bodies	Images	Deep learning network Water net	Accuracy and Loss	DL classifies the water bodies accurately by predicting lakes, ponds, clean water and other water sources.
Vellingiri et al., (2023)	Cauvery region	Physical and chemical indicators	Federated Learning	Accuracy, Precision, recall	RF and FL estimates the water quality effectively.

Draitsas & Trikga (2023)	Public dataset	Physical and chemical	ML models	Area under curve, precision and recall	Stacked model with SMOTE algorithm estimate the water quality effectively than other methods.
Chinnapan et al., (2023)	Chlorine and fluorine concentration	Chemical	Fuzzy set with decision tree	Area under curve, precision and recall	As compared to SVM, DT with fuzzy estimate the chlorine concentration effectively.
Vilas Khaire (2024)	Telangana	Physical and chemicals	ML models	Recall, Precision and F1	PCA with RF outperforms SVR, KNN and SGD
TR et al., (2024)	Public dataset	Physiochemical	Gradient boost multiclassification	Accuracy, sensitivity and specificity	Triple stage feature extraction with gradient boost enhanced water estimation.
Pandya et al., (2025)					

3. Paper Contribution

Based on this, this paper proposed a dual stage feature selection and tuned machine learning models for WQI analysis. This paper utilized the following techniques for WQI analysis:

- It performed a relational analysis between the physical and chemical indicators and water quality using dual stage approach.
- In the first stage, the filtering-based technique called Relief algorithm is used to select top five WQI indicators.
- Then, in the second stage, the meta heuristic algorithm called grey wolf optimization algorithm was used to select the top three WQI indicators.
- The GWO also performs the hyper parameter tuning of ML models to enhance the model performance.

This analysis aims to minimize the number of WQ indicators for observing and estimating the water quality accurately using machine learning models.

4. Proposed Work

This section elaborates on the complete workflow proposed for water quality classification, encompassing preprocessing, feature selection, model training, hyperparameter optimization, and evaluation. The methodology is designed to ensure both accuracy and interpretability in identifying potable water samples based on physicochemical parameters.

Figure 3. Propose Work flow Chart

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Overall Pseudocode 9: Complete Pipeline
Load Dataset
→ Preprocess Data:
- Impute NaNs
- Remove low-variance features
    
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- Rename labels
- Apply Relief Algorithm
- Use GWO to select optimal feature subset
- For each ML model:
 - Train model on selected features
 - Optimize hyperparameters using GWO
 - Evaluate performance using Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1
- Compare and select best model

characteristics are removed because they don't aid in learning. Consider the feature column X_j . It is eliminated if:

$$\text{Var}(X_j) = 0 \quad (2)$$

Pseudocode 2: Remove Non-informative Features

For each feature column j:

If variance (column j) == 0 or sum (column j) == 0:

Remove column j from dataset

3.1 Data Preprocessing

The initial phase involves preprocessing the raw water quality data to ensure that the subsequent analysis and model training stages are built on a reliable foundation.

3.1.1 Missing Value Imputation

Missing values in real-world water quality databases are frequently the result of sensor failures, measurement errors, or recording omissions. Instead of deleting such data points, we use mean imputation to replace each missing value with the mean of the relevant column. The mathematical transformation for a missing value x_{ij} is:

$$x_{ij} = \begin{cases} x_{ij}, & \text{if } x_{ij} \neq NaN \\ \mu_j = \frac{1}{n_j} \sum_{k=1}^{n_j} x_{kj}, & \text{if } x_{ij} = NaN \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Pseudocode 1: Mean Imputation

For each feature column j in dataset:

If any value x_{ij} is NaN:

Compute μ_j non-NaN values in column j

Replace all NaNs in column j with μ_j

This preserves the sample size and ensures consistent feature scaling.

3.1.2 Elimination of Non-Informative Features

Some characteristics could be fully composed of zeros or have zero variance, meaning that all values are the same across samples. These

Removing these attributes reduces computational overhead and enhances model generalization by eliminating redundancy.

3.1.3 Semantic Labelling

The binary class "Potability," where 1 denotes potable water and 0 denotes non-potable, is the dataset's target label. The semantic terms "Potable" and "Non-Potable" are used in place of these quantitative labels to improve clarity during analysis, visualisation, and reporting. This modification enhances interpretability during confusion matrix analysis and cross-tabulation without affecting model performance.

Pseudocode 3: Label Encoding

For each sample in dataset:

If target == 1:

Label = 'Potable'

Else:

Label = 'non-potable'

3.2 Hybrid Feature Selection Approach

Relief and grey wolf optimization algorithm are used to reduce the feature dimensionality and thereby enhancing the model accuracy. Relief algorithm performs a filter-based approach to determine top five attributes that are highly correlated to classification. While GWO is a wrapper-based approach that selects top three attributes from the relief algorithm for final estimation of water quality using tuned models.

3.2.1 Relief Algorithm

Relief is a univariate feature ranking method that assesses each attribute according to how well it distinguishes between neighbouring samples of various classes. Relief determines the closest hit (same class) and closest miss (different class) for a randomly chosen instance x_i and modifies feature weights appropriately:

$W[A] = W[A] - diff(A, x_i, nearestHit) + diff(A, x_i, nearestMiss)$	(3)
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Pseudocode 4: Relief Algorithm

Initialize weight vector $W = 0$ for all features
 For m randomly selected instances x_i :
 Find nearestHit = nearest neighbor of same class
 Find nearestMiss = nearest neighbor of different class
 For each feature A :
 Calculate $W[A]$
 Select top-ranked features based on W

For continuous features, the absolute difference is usually calculated using the function $diff$. Higher weight features prioritize selection and are more discriminative. Relief provides quick initial filtering, but it misses inter-feature relationships.

3.2.2 Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO)

To overcome Relief's limitations, we employ GWO, a nature-inspired metaheuristic that mimics grey wolf hunting behaviour, to improve the chosen attributes. Wolves are categorised as alpha (α), beta (β), delta (δ), and omega (ω) to illustrate the hierarchy of solutions in GWO. Each wolf (solution) is represented by a binary vector that indicates whether or not certain features are present.

Each wolf's position is adjusted according to its distance from the top three possibilities, as follows:

$\vec{D}_\alpha = \vec{C}_1 \cdot \vec{X}_\alpha - \vec{X} $	(4)
$X1 = \vec{X}_\alpha - \vec{A}_1 * \vec{D}_\alpha$	(5)
$\vec{D}_\beta = \vec{C}_2 \cdot \vec{X}_\beta - \vec{X} $	(6)
$X2 = \vec{X}_\beta - \vec{A}_2 * \vec{D}_\beta$	(7)
$\vec{D}_\delta = \vec{C}_3 \cdot \vec{X}_\delta - \vec{X} $	(8)
$X3 = \vec{X}_\delta - \vec{A}_3 * \vec{D}_\delta$	(9)

Where:

- $\vec{X}_\alpha, \vec{X}_\beta$ and \vec{X}_δ are the best three solutions.

- \vec{A} , and \vec{C} are adaptive coefficient vectors controlling exploration and exploitation.

Pseudocode 5: GWO for Feature Selection

Initialize population of wolves (binary vectors of length d)

Evaluate fitness of each wolf using cross-validation accuracy

For $t = 1$ to MaxIterations:

Identify alpha, beta, delta wolves (best three)

For each wolf:

Update position based on alpha, beta, delta using:

$$X_{new} = \frac{X1 + X2 + X3}{3}$$

Convert X_{new} to binary via sigmoid transfer

Update population

Return feature subset corresponding to alpha wolf

A sigmoid function maps the continuous position values to binary values for feature inclusion decisions.

3.3 Model Training and GWO-Based Hyperparameter Optimization

Following feature selection, we train four different ML models with diverse learning strategies. Each model's performance is maximized using GWO-based hyperparameter tuning.

Pseudocode 6: Model Training

For each model in {KNN, DT, RF, SVR}:

Use selected features to train model on training data

Store model for hyperparameter tuning

Each model has specific parameters:

- KNN: k (number of neighbours)
- DT: max_depth, split criterion
- RF: n_estimators, max_features
- SVR: C, kernel type, gamma

3.3.1 Candidate Models

1. K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN)

KNN is a non-parametric technique that uses the k-nearest neighbours' majority vote to classify an instance. One crucial hyperparameter that is optimised with GWO is the value of k.

$$\hat{y} = \arg \max_{c \in C} \sum_{i \in N_k(x)} \delta(y_i, c) \quad (10)$$

2. Decision Tree (DT)

Based on feature criteria that optimise information acquisition or minimise impurity as determined by the Gini index, DTs divide the dataset into subsets:

$$Gini(t) = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^c (p_i)^2 \quad (11)$$

3. Random Forest (RF)

Multiple DTs trained on bootstrapped datasets with random feature subsets make up the ensemble approach known as RF. The ultimate prediction is determined by the majority vote of the trees.

$$\hat{y} = mode(\{h_i(x)\}_{i=1}^T) \quad (12)$$

4. Support Vector Regression (SVR)

SVR can be modified for classification by thresholding the decision function, even though it is usually used for regression. Finding a hyperplane with the largest margin is the aim:

$$f(x) = w^T x + b \quad (13)$$

The penalty parameter CC and kernel parameters are tuned using GWO.

3.3.2 Hyperparameter Tuning with GWO

Each ML model has a set of hyperparameters that are crucial for achieving optimal performance. GWO is applied as a global optimizer to identify the best set of hyperparameters. The objective function is defined as:

$$Fitness = 1 - Accuracy_{cv} \quad (14)$$

Where $Accuracy_{cv}$ is the mean classification accuracy obtained via k-fold cross-validation (typically k=5) on the training dataset. Each wolf encodes a candidate hyperparameter vector (e.g., k in KNN, max depth in DT, number of trees in RF, CC, γ gamma, and kernel type in

SVR). The optimizer iteratively updates the population to converge toward the hyperparameter set that yields the highest validation performance.

Pseudocode 7: GWO for Hyperparameter Tuning

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Define search space for model parameters

Initialize population of wolves (each representing a hyperparameter set)

For each wolf:

    Train model using given parameters

    Evaluate performance using k-fold cross-validation

Calculate fitness using equations 14

For t = 1 to MaxIterations:

    Identify alpha, beta, delta wolves

    For each wolf:

        Update position using GWO equations

        Evaluate new fitness values

Return hyperparameter set from alpha wolf

Train final model with optimal hyperparameters

This procedure is repeated separately for each ML model.
    
```

3.4 Performance Evaluation

After training and optimization, each model is evaluated using standard classification metrics to ensure balanced performance:

- **Accuracy:** Proportion of correctly predicted samples.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (15)$$

- **Precision:** Proportion of true positives among all positive predictions.

$$Precision = TP / (TP + FP) \quad (16)$$

Recall (Sensitivity): Proportion of actual positives correctly identified.

$$Recall = TP / (TP + FN) \quad (17)$$

- **F1-Score:** Harmonic mean of precision and recall.

$F1 - Score = \frac{2 * Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (18)$

These metrics collectively evaluate the models on different aspects, such as false alarms (precision) and missed detections (recall), providing a holistic assessment of model reliability in practical deployment scenarios.

Pseudocode 8: Metrics Evaluation

For each trained model:

- Predict labels on test set
- Compute TP, TN, FP, FN
- Compute:
 - Accuracy
 - Precision
 - Recall
 - F1-Score
- Report results

5. Results and Discussion

This section presents a comprehensive analysis of the proposed dual-stage feature selection approach for water quality prediction. The experimental evaluation includes dataset distribution, feature importance ranking using Relief, further optimization with Grey Wolf Optimization (GWO), and performance comparison across four machine learning models: K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN), Decision Tree (DT), Random Forest (RF), and Support Vector Regression (SVR).

5.1 Dataset and Class Distribution

The proposed dual-stage feature selection analysis was carried out using MATLAB software version R2023b.

With the help of the publicly available water potability dataset from Kaggle, the proposed analysis was carried out. The dataset comprises physiochemical properties of water samples and their potability conditions as binary target variables 1 and 0. Here, 1 indicates the safe zone, and 0 indicates not safe for drinking conditions.

Figure 4. class distribution

Figure 4 shows the class distribution of the water samples in the dataset. It shows that the dataset has more non-potable water samples, i.e., 1978 non-potable water samples are present as compared to 1278 potable water samples. This imbalance will influence the classifier performance towards the non-potable class.

5.2 Feature Selection with Relief Algorithm

The most influencing attributes in estimating the water quality was determined using the relief algorithm in first stage. The Relief algorithm evaluate the attribute by comparing the input features with respect to the target output using nearest neighbouring algorithm. Based on this, the top five features that influence the water quality estimation is presented in figure 2.

Figure 5. Relief feature selection

Among nine attributes, Turbidity, hardness, solids organic carbon and conductivity are the most influential parameters in water quality estimation. In particular, solids, turbidity and hardness are highly influencing the estimation as it has higher weights as compared to the conductivity and organic carbon. The highest weight denotes the stronger correlation between target variable and the attribute.

5.3 Optimization with Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO)

Grey wolf optimization utilized for two processes namely feature selection and ML model parameters. The five attributes from relief algorithm were further refined by GWO and it selects turbidity, solids and hardness were the most influential parameters.

With these influential parameters and tuned ML parameters from GWO that is number of neighbours in KNN, max depth for DT, number of estimators in RF, ensuring an optimal balance between performance and complexity. Based on this information, the final classification is performed.

5.4 Confusion Matrix Analysis

The tuned ML model performances were analysed using confusion matrix and its corresponding confusion charts are presented in the figure 6 to 9. These charts give information about the correctly and wrongly classified classes.

Figure 7 KNN

As compared to DT, KNN improved its true positive rate by identifying 281 samples. It is due to the Relief based feature selection process.

Figure 6 DT

The tuned DT can accurately identify 1,947 non-potable classes and 107 potable classes. This shows that the DT is slightly to lower sensitivity.

Figure 8. RF

As compared to KNN and DT, Random Forest strongly classified both potable and non-potable classes. Due to its correctly identification of both samples accurately.

Figure 9 SVR

Among these four models, SVR model performance is not optimal as it cannot identify potable water samples accurately with tuned parameters and influential parameters. This shows that the SVR models require more attributes to enhance its performance.

5.4 Model Performance Comparison

The traditional classification metrics like accuracy, precision, recall and sensitivity were used to assess proposed feature selection and ML hyper parameters tuning. The corresponding evaluation metrics of four ML models namely: KNN, DT, SVR and RF was presented in figure 10.

KNN and D achieved the highest overall accuracy (~65%), indicating reliable performance when combined with the selected features.

RF and SVR demonstrated lower accuracy and precision, despite high recall, which may indicate over-prediction of the minority class (potable water).

Sensitivity was better for KNN than DT, suggesting it is more effective at correctly identifying potable samples.

5.6 Observations and Insights

The main objective of this paper is to estimate the water quality with minimal attributes for estimation. To achieve this, the dual stage feature selection and hyperparameter tuning was proposed and its performance were evaluated. The performance evaluation showed the following insights.

- The dual-stage i.e Relief and GWO feature selection approach significantly reduced dimensionality without sacrificing accuracy.
- Despite class imbalance, KNN and RF showed promising potential in real-world water quality estimation tasks.
- The lower performance of SVR emphasizes the importance of model selection and tuning, especially when applied to classification tasks with regression-based models.

The experimental results validate the efficacy of the proposed method. Feature dimensionality was effectively reduced from full input to three optimized features without major degradation in performance. The hybrid use of filter-based and nature-inspired optimization enhanced the generalization ability of the machine learning models, particularly in handling imbalanced datasets.

6. Conclusion

This work proposed a dual-stage feature selection approach for water quality estimation, combining filter and wrapper-based methods. Initially, the filter-based technique identified the top five attributes most relevant to water quality prediction. From these, Grey Wolf Optimization (GWO) was employed to select the three most significant attributes and simultaneously optimize the parameters of the machine learning model. By integrating feature selection and hyperparameter tuning, the proposed method enhances the model's predictive performance and ensures the reliability of the selected attributes. The use of GWO in both stages confirms its effectiveness in improving water quality estimation.

7. Future works

In future, the proposed work can be realized by analysing the real time datasets using Internet of Things.

References

1. (No date) Valuing water | 2021 World Water Development Report. Available at: <https://www.unesco.org/reports/wwdr/2021/en> (Accessed: 29 July 2025).

2. (No date a) Progress on household drinking water, sanitation and hygiene, 2000-2020: Five years into the sdgs - UNICEF data. Available at: <https://data.unicef.org/resources/progress-on-household-drinking-water-sanitation-and-hygiene-2000-2020/> (Accessed: 29 July 2025).
3. Programme, U.W.W.A., Connor and Unesco (1970) UN World Water Development Report 2019 - leaving no one behind, UNESCO.org. Available at: <https://www.unesco.org/en/wwap/wwdr/2019> (Accessed: 29 July 2025).
4. Chapman, D. (1996). *Water Quality Assessments: A Guide to the Use of Biota, Sediments and Water in Environmental Monitoring* (2nd ed.). UNEP/WHO/UNESCO.
5. Kannel, P. R., Lee, S., Lee, Y. S., Kanel, S. R., & Khan, S. P. (2007). Application of water quality indices and dissolved oxygen as indicators for river water classification and urban impact assessment. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 132(1-3), 93–110. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-006-9505-1>
6. Sutadian, A. D., Muttill, N., Yilmaz, A. G., & Perera, B. J. C. (2016). Development of river water quality indices—a review. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 188(1), 58. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-015-5050-0>
7. Ma, Y., Song, K., Wen, Z., Liu, G., Shang, Y., Lyu, L., ... & Hou, J. (2021). Remote sensing of turbidity for lakes in northeast China using Sentinel-2 images with machine learning algorithms. *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, 14, 9132-9146.
8. Kouadri, S., Elbeltagi, A., Islam, A. R. M. T., & Kateb, S. (2021). Performance of machine learning methods in predicting water quality index based on irregular data set: application on Illizi region (Algerian southeast). *Applied Water Science*, 11(12), 190.
9. Al-Sulttani, A. O., Al-Mukhtar, M., Roomi, A. B., Farooque, A. A., Khedher, K. M., & Yaseen, Z. M. (2021). Proposition of new ensemble data-intelligence models for surface water quality prediction. *IEEE Access*, 9, 108527-108541.
10. Kaur, A., Khurana, M., Kaur, P., & Kaur, M. (2021, April). Classification and analysis of water quality using machine learning algorithms. In *Proceedings of International Conference on Communication, Circuits, and Systems: IC3S 2020* (pp. 389-398). Singapore: Springer Singapore.
11. Rodríguez, R., Pastorini, M., Etcheverry, L., Chreties, C., Fossati, M., Castro, A., & Gorgoglione, A. (2021). Water-quality data imputation with a high percentage of missing values: A machine learning approach. *Sustainability*, 13(11), 6318.
12. Aslam, B., Maqsoom, A., Cheema, A. H., Ullah, F., Alharbi, A., & Imran, M. (2022). Water quality management using hybrid machine learning and data mining algorithms: An indexing approach. *IEEE Access*, 10, 119692-119705.
13. Suwadi, N. A., Derbali, M., Sani, N. S., Lam, M. C., Arshad, H., Khan, I., & Kim, K. I. (2022). An optimized approach for predicting water quality features based on machine learning. *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*, 2022(1), 3397972.
14. Juna, A., Umer, M., Sadiq, S., Karamti, H., Eshmawi, A. A., Mohamed, A., & Ashraf, I. (2022). Water quality prediction using KNN imputer and multilayer perceptron. *Water*, 14(17), 2592.
15. Malek, N. H. A., Wan Yaacob, W. F., Md Nasir, S. A., & Shaadan, N. (2022). Prediction of water quality classification of the Kelantan River Basin, Malaysia, using machine learning techniques. *Water*, 14(7), 1067.
16. Ajayi, O. O., Bagula, A. B., Maluleke, H. C., Gaffoor, Z., Jovanovic, N., & Pietersen, K. C. (2022). Waternet: A network for monitoring and assessing water quality for drinking and irrigation purposes. *IEEE Access*, 10, 48318-48337.

17. Chakravarthy, S. S., Bharanidharan, N., Venkatesan, V. K., Abbas, M., Rajaguru, H., Mahesh, T. R., & Venkatesan, K. (2023). Prediction of water quality using SoftMax-ELM optimized using adaptive crow-search algorithm. *IEEE Access*, 11, 140900-140913.
18. Asghar, S., Gilanie, G., Saddique, M., Ullah, H., Mohamed, H. G., Abbasi, I. A., & Abbas, M. (2023). Water classification using convolutional neural network. *IEEE Access*, 11, 78601-78612.
19. Vellingiri, J., Kalaivanan, K., Gopinath, M. P., & Gobinath, C. (2023). Strategies for classifying water quality in the Cauvery River using a federated learning technique. *International Journal of Cognitive Computing in Engineering*, 4, 187-193.
20. Draitsas, E., & Trigka, M. (2023). Efficient data-driven machine learning models for water quality prediction. *Computation*, 11(2), 16.
21. Chinnappan, C. V., John William, A. D., Nidamanuri, S. K. C., Jayalakshmi, S., Bogani, R., Thanapal, P., ... & Syed Masood, J. A. I. (2023). IoT-enabled chlorine level assessment and prediction in water monitoring system using machine learning. *Electronics*, 12(6), 1458.
22. Vilas Khaire, N. (2024). Water Quality Analysis Using Machine Learning (Doctoral dissertation, Dublin Business School).
23. TR, M., Bhatia Khan, S., Balajee, A., Almusharraf, A., Gadekallu, T. R., Albalawi, E., & Kumar V, V. (2024). Water quality level estimation using IoT sensors and probabilistic machine learning model. *Hydrology Research*, 55(7), 775-789.
24. Pandya, J. K., Khandelwal, S. S., Tipu, R. K., & Pandya, K. S. (2025). Advancing Water Quality Management: An Integrated Approach Using Ensemble Machine Learning and Real-Time Interactive Visualization. *IEEE Access*.